

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR FORMING A TRADING STRATEGY AS A COMPONENT OF OPERATIONAL MARKETING

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Abstract

The article considers approaches to the definition of a marketing strategy, the concept of a marketing strategy is formed, the tasks of developing a product strategy, factors, influencing the formation of a commodity strategy, an algorithm for developing a commodity strategy for a trading enterprise has been developed.

Keywords: marketing strategy, trade marketing strategy, operational marketing, marketing mix, trade marketing tasks, factors, algorithm.

For modern trading enterprises operating in a highly competitive and dynamically developing market environment, ensuring and maintaining the required level of competitiveness can only be achieved with the right product strategy.

It occupies a special place in marketing as a component of the product policy in the management system of the production and marketing activities of the enterprise. A well-thought-out product strategy is focused on high-quality satisfaction of consumer demand.

Previous studies show that product strategy, being a component of operational marketing, almost always affects the nature and characteristics of alternative components of the marketing mix. At the strategic level of development of a trading company, product strategy is the most important competitive advantage.

Despite the high importance of decisions in the field of product strategy formation, in practice there is a one-sided approach to this process. In this regard, the purpose of the present study is to study the problems associated with the use of a strategic approach by commercial enterprises.

The main tool for the strategic management of the organization's development is the marketing strategy. [1, 8, 14]

There are different approaches to the definition of "marketing strategy". Many authors, using two terminal

combinations "marketing strategy" and "marketing strategy", came to the conclusion that it is worth agreeing with the opinion of E.P. Golubkov, who claims that "a marketing strategy is the same as a marketing strategy" [2]. According to E.A. Utkin, marketing strategy is "an integral part of the entire strategic management of an enterprise, it is a plan for its business activity." Its main task is to maintain and develop the production process, the intellectual potential of the company's employees, to increase the range and quality of manufactured goods, to develop new markets, increase sales and, ultimately, to increase the efficiency of activities [3]. However, a number of authors interpret the concept of "marketing strategy" as a set of interrelated activities, with the help of which the company hopes to achieve its goals. Thus, O. Walker defines a marketing strategy as "effectively distributed and coordinated market resources and activities to perform the tasks of a firm in a particular product market [3]. The same feature is noted by one of the leading experts in the field of marketing F. Kotler in his famous work "Fundamentals of Marketing", giving the following definition: "Marketing strategy is a logical scheme of marketing activities with which the company hopes to fulfill its marketing tasks" [5]. According to F. Kotler [5], the marketing strategy consists of three parts (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Philip Kotler Marketing New Values [5]

Based on the presented approach, it can be argued that the author puts the marketing mix into the basis of the marketing strategy. Thus, the marketing strategy is

directly related to the sale of goods on the market, taking on an operational character. In the Modern Dictionary of Economics, marketing strategy is defined as "a

company's marketing measures for the sustainable promotion of its products to the market, including goal setting, analysis, planning of marketing activities, monitoring" [3]. A number of authors consider "marketing strategy" as planning the marketing mix (marketing mix). So, S.E. Chernov believes that "a marketing strategy is developed for each target market with the definition of strategic settings for products, distribution channels, methods of promoting products, prices, other elements of the marketing mix, as well as the marketing budget" [3].

The same feature is also noted by J. O'Shaughnessy, who believes that "the marketing strategy is a broad concept of how a product, price, promotion and distribution should function in a coordinated manner in order to overcome the opposition to achieving marketing objectives" [3]. In other words, the content of the marketing strategy shows how the proposed key characteristics of the firm's product offering (product / service, price, promotion and distribution) should lead to the achievement of marketing and enterprise goals. In our opinion, some researchers define marketing strategy as the development of an effective marketing program for a specific target market. So, G.L. Bagiev believes that a marketing strategy is a general program of marketing activities in target markets. It includes the main directions of the company's marketing activities and the tools of the marketing mix (marketing mix), with the help of which they develop and implement marketing activities to achieve their goals [3]. T.A. Gaidenko gives, in our opinion, the clearest definition of marketing strategy, defining it as "an analysis of the company's capabilities in the market, the choice of a system of goals, the development and formulation of plans and the implementation of marketing activities aimed at reducing market risk, ensuring long-term and sustainable development of the enterprise" [3, 12]. According to A.V. Zavgorodney and D.O. Yampolskaya, the marketing strategy includes three components [3]:

1. The strategy for choosing the target market, or the segmentation strategy.
2. Strategy for positioning and creating a competitive advantage.

3. The strategy for the existence of a product (brand) is a mix strategy that consists of a set of measures related to the product, price, promotion, distribution [3, 12].

From the foregoing, it follows that when implementing a marketing strategy, the needs of the consumer are taken as the basis. It is the identification of needs and their further satisfaction that underlies the marketing strategy. Based on the above statements, we believe that the essential component of the "marketing strategy" is applicable to the product marketing strategy, which is based on the main tools of strategic management of the trade organization; development of effective (planning) marketing activities (marketing mix); promotion (realization) of goods on the market (characteristics of the product offer of the enterprise); program of marketing activities of the enterprise; achievement of marketing goals; choice of target market; meeting the needs (needs) of consumers; struggle for the consumer by satisfying his needs; identification of potential buyers. We believe that non-use of the product strategy by trading enterprises leads to instability of the assortment structure due to the impact of random or incoming current factors, loss of control over the competitiveness and commercial effectiveness of goods. In such cases, current marketing decisions are often based solely on intuition, and not on a sober calculation that takes into account long-term interests. On the contrary, a well-thought-out product strategy not only allows you to optimize the process of updating the product range, but also serves as a kind of indicator for the company's management of the general direction of actions that can correct current situations.

Commodity strategy is an integral part of the economic and marketing policy of the enterprise [13]. Because of this, the principle "the product chooses the buyer" in combination with the creation of a wide range of choices for buyers should be laid directly in production. The system of construction, modeling, design, incentive mechanisms and production organization should be oriented towards a specific potential buyer. Based on this, in our opinion, the objectives of developing a product strategy can be the following: (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The tasks of developing a product strategy

When forming a commodity strategy, it is necessary to observe a number of conditions: to have a clear idea of the goals of production, marketing and export in the future, the strategy of the production and marketing activities of the enterprise; know the market and the nature of its requirements well; be aware of opportunities and resources now and in the future. Since market success is the main criterion for assessing the activities of enterprises, and their market opportunities are predetermined by a properly developed and consistently implemented product policy, it is on the basis of studying the market and development prospects that an enterprise receives initial information for solving issues related to the formation, management and its improvement. At any economic level, a strategic approach is necessary to solve the problems of a commodity strategy. The commodity strategy determines the long-term course of the enterprise, designed for the future and providing for the solution of fundamental problems. This is the basis of the company's commercial policy.

The factors influencing the formation of a commodity strategy are divided into two groups: internal and external. In this context, internal factors reflect the constraints associated with making decisions on the formation of a product strategy.

External factors represent opportunities for choosing a particular strategy and tactics. Each of these groups of factors is represented by two more subgroups.

However, in our opinion, this list of factors influencing the formation of a commodity strategy is incomplete and should be presented more specifically. And since the product strategy is one of the components of marketing activities, the presented internal and external marketing factors, in turn, directly or indirectly affect not only the enterprise, but also influence the formation of the product strategy. We are of the opinion of marketers who recommend that when developing and implementing a product strategy, focus on commercially

proven approaches that can be very useful for entrepreneurs.

1. It is fundamentally important, especially when it comes to serial and mass-produced goods, to ensure that in the eyes of the buyer they compare favorably with the goods of competing firms due to corporate identity, packaging, color, special design elements and other, at first glance, insignificant aspects.

2. From a number of products manufactured by the enterprise, in certain situations it is advisable to choose one product that may be attractive to many buyers, and provide this product with the so-called concentrated marketing. A product successfully introduced to the market in this way can, like a locomotive, "bring" other products of the enterprise to the market, having created a favorable image for them in advance.

3. Using differentiated marketing, you can try to create varieties of the same product for different market segments, developing Internal Factors External Demographics Macroenvironment Microenvironment Marketing (4p) Management political competitors product personnel suppliers price social cultural natural technological consumers intermediaries laws and government bodies trade unions promotion place sales physical environment process appropriate marketing programs and provide, using the terminology of football, pressure against competitors across the field.

Product narrow specialization justifies itself if its enterprise operates in a rather narrow market segment, when the demand for one product continues to grow for a long time. Sometimes narrow specialization, as a variant of a product strategy, is perceived as a forced measure, since the enterprise does not have sufficient resources to carry out successful work on a wide range of product nomenclature due to the specifics of the product itself, as well as the features of the technological process. The reason may be a deep segmentation of the market for this product. In some cases, narrow specialization is optimal for the efficient operation of a small

enterprise or when an enterprise periodically changes its narrow specialization, using it to develop new markets or adapting to the changing nature of demand.

5. High results can be achieved when entering the market with a new product (market novelty product).

6. It can be very fruitful to find new areas of use for an already manufactured product, supported by a large advertising campaign and other sales promotion activities.

7. You can achieve market advantages by highlighting your products as special, different from competitors' products, due to specific consumer properties, especially improved quality, superiority of raw materials, a complex of services accompanying the product (systemic sale).

The main guideline in the formation of a product strategy is (with all the importance of other categories) the achievement of a competitive advantage of the enterprise in the long term. Having chosen one or another alternative of a product strategy, a trading company must "fill" it with specific content - the corresponding product or product range, that is, a group of products that are closely related to each other in at least one of the signs: joint use, a common market segment, a common distribution channel, similar price range.

Thus, the product strategy cannot be separated from the actual conditions of the enterprise, the specifics of the external marketing environment. However, as practice shows, trade enterprises located in the same market and economic conditions solve their commodity problems in different ways. Some show complete confusion and helplessness. Others, following the concept of marketing, find promising ways, developing trading strategies, and achieve some success. In modern conditions of competition, it is necessary that the commodity strategy of the enterprise be formed taking into account the prospects for the development of its activities.

Compliance of the assortment with the strategic goals of the business is the main task of the commodity strategy of the enterprise. Commodity strategy helps the company to strengthen its position among competitors, as it allows you to take into account the specific features of the trading company, its strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats. The specific task of the strategy for a trading enterprise is the formation of a product range that satisfies the prevailing market conditions and goals. At the same time, an important element of the product strategy is bringing the product to the consumer, which consists in determining the most attractive market segment.

We have developed an algorithm for developing a commodity strategy for a trading enterprise.

The first step in developing a product strategy is to set goals for the organization. The strategy is designed to ensure the adaptation of the enterprise to a rapidly changing environment, so it must answer the following questions: a) what, in what quantity and what quality to produce and sell; b) how and on what markets to work; c) what actions, how and why should be carried out in the first place.

The second stage in the development of a commodity strategy is the analysis of the internal state and

external environment of the Lgovskoye Production Association. The results of the assessment of external opportunities and dangers can be expressed through the impact of groups of factors: economic, political, market, competitive, international, social, production and technological. Among the factors of the last group, one should single out the state of production in the sections of technological chains external to the enterprise, the level of technology of competitors, and the possibilities of new technological developments. Further, it is determined to what extent the enterprise has internal forces to take advantage of external opportunities, and also identifies internal weaknesses that can complicate problems associated with external dangers. It considers the structure and organizational potential of the enterprise, the use of existing production potential, the state of distribution channels and after-sales service networks. As a result of the analysis, the strategy is developed on the basis of strengths (while adding weaknesses), while taking into account external sources of opportunities and dangers.

The third stage in the development of a product strategy is a strategic analysis of manufactured goods, which requires a preliminary collection of diagnostic information. Strategic analysis of manufactured goods involves the collection of diagnostic information and its analysis.

The fourth stage in the development of a product strategy is the analysis of priorities for manufactured goods. Given the different importance of goods for the enterprise in the future, it is necessary to establish the strategic importance of each type of product or group of goods. Prioritization is necessary to allocate resources in the development and implementation of the product.

The fifth stage in the development of a product strategy is the definition of an assortment policy.

The sixth stage is the formation of a product range. Having chosen one or another assortment policy, the management of the Lgovskoye Production Association must "fill" it with specific content - the relevant services or product range, i.e. a group of goods that are closely related to each other by at least one of the signs: associated (joint) use, common market segment, common distribution channel, similar price range.

The seventh stage is the implementation and implementation of the product strategy. Responsibilities for the implementation and implementation of a product strategy vary according to the organizational levels of management. The main tasks at the lowest level are: market analysis, establishing target markets, choosing a positional strategy, analyzing products and strategies, identifying new product needs, managing and coordinating marketing activities for a product or brand. At the same level, a plan is developed for a product or brand.

The eighth stage involves the coordination of work on the adopted product strategy. As the centerpiece of the business, product strategy must be combined with a marketing system that includes pricing, distribution and promotion of goods and services.

Thus, the development of a commodity strategy for a commercial enterprise is currently becoming the

basis of the management process. In today's unstable financial situation, an enterprise must not only respond to changes in the external environment, but also anticipate these changes.

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